

ASSESSING FLUID AND FIBER CONSUMPTION AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN IN DISTRICT MARDAN, PAKISTAN: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

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Abstract

Dietary deficiencies can affect pregnancy outcomes and neonatal health. Intake of several nutrients like dietary fiber and also stay hydrated and drinking water were also important for healthy pregnant women. Encouraging adequate intake of fiber and fluid during pregnancy is essential yet often overlooked. The study on fluid and fiber intake during pregnancy in Mardan revealed that a majority of pregnant women experienced common pregnancy-related conditions such as thirst, dark-colored urine, dizziness, headaches, and digestive issues, including constipation and abdominal discomfort. The daily fluid intake was generally low, with nearly equal proportions of women drinking 1–4 or 4–8 glasses of water. The high milk consumption and notable consumption of green tea, fruit juice, and soft drinks indicate varying beverage choices during pregnancy. Fiber intake changes, with most women consuming vegetables, fruits, beans, and nuts, while whole grains and refined grains were less commonly consumed. Pregnant women should aim for at least 8 glasses of water per day to ensure proper hydration, which can help alleviate symptoms such as thirst, dark-colored urine, and dizziness. Additionally, promoting a more balanced fiber consumption is crucial and they should consume adequate vegetables, fruits, beans, nuts, and whole grains in the diet can help improve digestion and alleviate constipation.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is a period in which women undergo significant hormonal and physiological changes. Globally, annually 140 million women become pregnant (Pritschet *et al.*, 2024) (Tretter, 2024). these changes are crucial in balancing the various bodily systems' functioning in relation to the needs of the fetus, and maternal health (KazemiDadkhah and Torabi, 2022). To complete this critical period,

adequate nutritional intake is paramount. The first thousand days of life, starting from conception and continuing through to 2 years of child are crucial period. Poor dietary consumption or deficiencies can effect pregnancy outcomes and neonatal health (MousaNaqash and Lim, 2019). Intake of several nutrients like dietary fiber and also stay hydrated and drinking water were also important for healthy

pregnant women (Miyake *et al.*, 2023). Encouraging adequate intake of fiber and fluid during pregnancy is essential yet often overlooked (Hage-Fransen *et al.*, 2021).

Water accounts for about 60~70% of a healthy adult's body weight. Water requirements increase as gestational age advances (Mulyani *et al.*, 2021). Water plays important role in numerous physiological functions during pregnancy the total water content expands from 6.5-8L to support fetus growth, formation of amniotic fluid and plasma volume (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Inadequate water intake during pregnancy causes dehydration which is associated with gestational diabetes, constipation, increased risk of preterm delivery and miscarriage (Ding *et al.*, 2021). This increase is vital for pregnant women as it supports the expansion of plasma volume, the formation of amniotic fluid, and the maturation of the placenta, all of which are essential for providing optimal conditions for the fetus's healthy growth and development (Lin *et al.*, 2024). Recommended daily intake of water for pregnant females is 3000mL/day for American, Canadian and Chinese population, while 31000mL/day for Australia and New Zealand (Pauley *et al.*, 2024), (Xie *et al.*, 2023).

Dietary fiber is crucial component of healthy diet during pregnancy intake with 28g recommended daily allowance during pregnancy (Pretorius and Palmer, 2020). Dietary fiber sources are cereals, whole grains, vegetables, fruits, legumes, roasted beans, nuts, and similar foods (Zerfu and Mekuria, 2019). Epidemiological research has indicated that higher dietary fiber intake is associated with a reduced risk of several chronic diseases (Miyake *et al.*, 2023). Consuming higher amounts of dietary fiber during this period not only enhances gut microbiome diversity but may also help prevent excessive weight gain, glucose intolerance, gestational hypertensive disorders, and constipation. and supporting regular bowel movements (Omoto *et al.*, 2024). Constipation is particularly common during pregnancy and the prevalence has been found to increase in the first and second trimester, and decrease in the third trimester. The prevalence of constipation reported to increase 11% to 40% (Reijonen *et al.*, 2022). Insufficient intake of fluids and fiber is a primary cause of this and other gastrointestinal symptoms like acid reflux,

which affects a large proportion of pregnant women (Liu *et al.*, 2023). Despite the well-established importance of fluid and fiber, many women do not meet the recommended daily intake (Thompson, 2021). Furthermore, while global guidelines exist, there is a notable scarcity of localized research on this topic, particularly in developing regions. This study aims to address this knowledge gap by assessing the fluid and fiber intake among antenatal females in District Mardan. The findings of this cross-sectional study will provide valuable insights into the dietary habits of pregnant women in this specific geographical area and will serve as a basis for developing targeted public health interventions to improve maternal and neonatal outcomes.

Materials and methods

Study design, location and duration

The cross-sectional study was carried out from pregnant women of Mardan. To study fluid and fiber intake from February 2024 to April 2024. Total 100 women were recruited for the study. A **non-probability grab sampling method** was used to enlist participants from Darulshifa hospital Mardan. A well-designed questionnaire was used to collect information from study participants. The questionnaire consists of general characteristics, their socioeconomic status and dietary behavior with aged 18-45. Women with medical conditions requiring specific diets e.g. women with diabetes and hypertension during pregnancy and with incomplete questionnaire were excluded. Dietary data, assessment was done with the help of a questionnaire. different food groups that provide fiber and the typical amounts consumed were noted. Different types of fluids and how much participant typically consume daily was also recorded. Statistical analysis to calculate frequency percentages and frequencies, which were then presented in tabular and graphical forms were constructed with Microsoft excel.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To examine the importance of fluid and fiber intake during pregnancy data was collected from the pregnant women of Mardan. Females were in age group 22-42. According to their occupation 59.1% were housewives and 43% were working women as shown in table 1

Table 1. Age and Occupation of Pregnant women

Variables	Categories	Percentage
Age	22-32	54%
	32-42	46%
Occupation	Housewife	59.1%
	Working women	40.9%

The study reported that (63.9%) of respondents experienced thirst. Additionally, (62.2%) of respondents noticing dark-colored urination, whereas (37.1%) did not noticed this condition. Regarding frequent urination, (55.2%) reported not experiencing it, while (44.8%) indicated they did experience frequent urination. For thirst ($p < 0.01$) and dark urination ($p < 0.05$) that are significantly more frequent than expected under a 50/50 distribution. **Frequent urination** ($p > 0.05$) does not show a statistically significant difference from the expected 50/50 distribution.as shown in Table 2, figure 1.

A study by McIntyre reported that **30-40%** of women **experience thirst** and frequent urination **25-35%** during pregnancy (McIntyre *et al.*, 2019). Another study reported 30% to 60%, signs of inadequate hydration by urinary markers, self-reported intake, or symptoms of dehydration (Xie *et al.*, 2023). (AbrarMohsin and Samad, 2023) from cross sectional study reported urinary inconsistency was (31.1%) in pregnant ladies. The **primary source of fluids was plain water**, accounting for over **60% of total intake in a study by**. **Urine concentration measurements indicated that a substantial proportion of participants were inadequately hydrated** (Bardosono *et al.*, 2016).

Table 2. Chi Square Test for qualitative variables of the study

Symptoms	Yes	No	χ^2	Significance
Thirst	63.9%	36.1%	7.84	$P < 0.01$
Dark Urination	62.2%	37.8%	5.76	$P < 0.05$
Frequent Urination	44.8	55.2%	1.0	$p > 0.05$
Dizziness	77%	23%	29.1	$p < 0.001$
Headache	58.6%)	58.6%	3.24	$p = 0.05$
Constipation	81.8%	18.25%	40.96	$p < 0.001$
Hard stool	66%	34%	10.24	$p < 0.01$
Constipation	81.8%	18.25%	40.96	$p < 0.001$
Hard stool	66%	34%	10.24	$p < 0.01$
Abdominal discomfort	81.8%	18.2%	40.9	$p < 0.001$
Blood in stool	66%	44%	21.1	$p < 0.001$
Frequent Diarrhea	78.8%	21.2%	33.64	$p < 0.001$

Headache and dizziness were reported among participants, with (77%) of women experiencing dizziness while standing and (23%) reporting no dizziness. Additionally, (58.6%) of pregnant women reported headaches, while (41.4%) did not. For dizziness: $\chi^2 = 29.16$, which is highly notable ($p < 0.001$). So, dizziness is significantly more frequent than expected. For headache: $\chi^2 = 3.24$, which is not quite significant at $p = 0.05$ (Table 2 Figure 1).

Changes during pregnancy often lead to discomfort for pregnant women that (46.7%) of these discomforts frequently include dizziness or headaches (Handayani and Maryam, 2024).

A cross sectional study also reported headache (53.4%) during pregnancy(Zimmermann *et al.*, 2023). Khoromi found that headache among pregnant women was (35%) (Khoromi, 2023).

Figure 1. Frequency percentage of dehydration symptoms among pregnant women from District Mardan,

Digestive issues among pregnant women reported that 81.8% experienced constipation, while 18.2% did not report and it was highly significant $p < 0.001$. Additionally, 66% of respondents noticed hard stools, whereas 34% did not and $p < 0.01$ (significant) as illustrated in (Table 2 Figure 2). A study findings of Lin et al., reported (79.3%) of participants had experienced and were aware of constipation during

pregnancy (Lin et al., 2024). A study by Rao et al., reported that about (40%) of women developed constipation during pregnancy (Rao et al., 2022). A cross sectional study reported 17-54% pregnant women had experience constipation during pregnancy (Parlas and Bilgic, 2024).

Figure 2. Symptoms of low fiber intake observed in pregnant females of District Mardan.

Some other digestive conditions experienced by pregnant women included abdominal discomfort, reported by (84.5%) of participants, while (15.5%) did not experience it and that was highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Regarding blood in stool (72.7%) did not notice it, while (27.3%) reported as yes and highly significant ($p < 0.001$). Regarding frequent diarrhea, the majority (78.8%) answered "no," while (21.2%) reported "yes" highly significant ($p < 0.001$) as shown

in Table 2 Figure 2. Rectal bleeding prevalence of 10-43% in the form of blood in stool during pregnancy was reported by (Prentice et al., 2021). Lin reported that 69.2% of participants experienced constipation which can lead to abdominal discomfort during pregnancy (Lin et al., 2024). Approximately 60% of pregnant women experience pelvic pain, which can contribute to abdominal discomfort (Shanshan et al., 2024). Newman study reported that 527 of 3693

pregnant women in a cross sectional study experienced diarrhea (14.3%) (Newman *et al.*, 2019). Fluid intake during pregnancy was reported as follows (50.1%) of women consumed 1-4 glasses of water per day, while (49%) consumed 4-8 glasses per day

(Figure 3). The Xie *et al.*, cross sectional reported that recommended daily water intake (about 2.3 liters for pregnant women) that around 8-9 glasses but only consume was 20% to 40% (Xie *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 3. Water intake and fluid intake from other sources by pregnant women

Green tea consumption was reported by (79%) of women, fruit juice consumption by (69%). Soft drinks consumption was (68%) during pregnancy and milk consumption by (90%) of women per day. Soft drinks consumption was high and milk consumption also increases that was (90%) as shown in figure 3. Lindberg *et al.*, reported that sugary drinks approximately 60% in early pregnancy milk and dairy products consumption also during early pregnancy (Lindberg, 2020). The current finding examines the tea consumption by pregnant ladies was (90%) per day. A cross sectional study also reported that women consume tea excessively (Wei, 2020).

Vegetable consumption as a source of fiber revealed that (89%) of respondents consumed one serving per day, while (11%) consumed two servings per day. For fruit intake, (78%) consumed one serving per day, and (21%) consumed half a serving. Regarding dried beans, (79%) consumed one serving per day, and (17%) consumed half a serving. For nuts, (72%) of women consumed one serving per day, (17%)

consumed half a serving, and (12%) consumed two servings per day (Figure 4). The current study reported that vegetable consumption per day (89%) and fruit (78%) consumed one serving per day during pregnancy. Fan *et al.*, reported that intake of fruits and vegetable with the high intake group consuming an average of 60%, while the low intake group consumed an average of 20% (Fan *et al.*, 2021).

The current study reported one serving per day consumption of fruits and vegetable was high during pregnancy. Cross sectional study by Stravik *et al.*, reported about (78%) of pregnant women consumption daily servings of fruits and vegetables (Stråvik *et al.*, 2019). Only 22% of women met the recommended intake of five or more servings per day. Smith reported that only 6.7% of pregnant women consumed the recommended intake of 1.5 cups of dried beans per week. That was also explore that higher dried bean intake was linked with increased intake of dietary fiber that reduce constipation during pregnancy (Smith, 2023).

Figure 4. Fiber intake from vegetable, fruits, dried beans and nuts by pregnant women in Mardan

Whole grain consumption, including rice, pasta, and muffins, was reported as follows as (53%) of participants consumed one serving per day, (26%) consumed 1.5 servings per day, and 21% consumed two a serving per day. Refined grains were consumed at 2 servings per day by (43%) of participants, 1 serving per day by (33%), and half a serving per day by (24%). Breakfast cereals were consumed at 1 serving per day by (17%) of participants, while (83%) consumed half a serving per day per day (Figure 4). That was also reported by (Stråvik *et al.*, 2019) (29%) of women consumed whole grains, while 45% had a diet rich in refined grains. Shrestha *et al.*, reported that less than (20%) of the daily intake of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains during pregnancy because they skip breakfast (Shrestha *et al.*, 2021). Fiber intake among

participants revealed that (44%) of women consumed 12-16 grams of fiber below average, (49.9%) consumed 16-20 grams that was normal, (4.2%) consumed greater than 20 grams normal, and (1.9%) consumed less than 12 grams (Figure 4). Zhang *et al.*, reported that only (29.5%) of participants met the recommended daily intake of 28 grams of fiber (Zhang *et al.*, 2021). Participants consumed 24.1 grams of fiber per day on average, with most intakes ranging from 19.0 to 29.7 grams. The cohort study by Fan *et al.*, reported that during pregnancy fiber intake was insufficient (Fan *et al.*, 2021). The median intake was 23.5 grams per day, which was below the recommended intake of 28 grams per day for pregnant women.

Figure 5. Fiber intake per gram by pregnant women per day in Mardan

CONCLUSION

The study on fluid and fiber intake during pregnancy in Mardan revealed that a majority of pregnant women experienced common pregnancy-related conditions such as thirst, dark-colored urine, dizziness, headaches, and digestive issues, including constipation and abdominal discomfort. The daily fluid intake was generally low, with nearly equal proportions of women drinking 1–4 or 4–8 glasses of water. The high milk consumption and notable consumption of green tea, fruit juice, and soft drinks indicate varying beverage choices during pregnancy. Fiber intake changes, with most women consuming vegetables, fruits, beans, and nuts, while whole grains and refined grains were less commonly consumed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Findings of the study on fluid and fiber intake during pregnancy in Mardan, several recommendations can be made. During pregnancy regularly monitoring headaches, dizziness, and abdominal discomfort should also be conducted, as these may indicate a need for dietary adjustments. First, increasing fluid intake is essential, as the study revealed that many women consumed insufficient water. Pregnant women should aim for at least 8 glasses of water per day to ensure proper hydration, which can help alleviate symptoms such as thirst, dark-colored urine, and dizziness. Reducing the intake of soft drinks, which was notably high in the study, is also important, as they can negatively affect maternal health due to their sugar content. Instead, pregnant women should be encouraged for healthier beverages such as water, milk, or herbal teas. Additionally, promoting a more balanced fiber consumption is crucial, as most women consumed adequate vegetables, fruits, beans, and nuts, but whole grains were less commonly consumed. Including more whole grains in the diet can help improve digestion and alleviate constipation.

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